

Gibbs' Paradox, Indistinguishability and Local Pressure Part II

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In Part I, we argued that the indistinguishability of particles used to resolve the Gibbs' paradox, for a gas with two equal volume chambers, separated by a wall, with the same number and type of gas particles, follows from the idea of pressure balance. We argued that this is a purely classical argument. Here, we consider the same problem from the point of view of minimal information associated with particle parameters directly linked to pressure balance and try to obtain an expression for entropy as \ln of the number of states. In other words, the particle parameters considered when counting states should be associated with the physical balance which creates physical equilibrium in the problem. Thus, it is not simply the counting of any allowed states, based on arbitrary properties of the states, with equal weighting or the loss of information which is pertinent, but rather these have to be associated with the creation of a balance (pressure balance in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas) which in turn leads to the creation of equilibrium, we argue.

Establishing the Particle Properties Needed for Equilibrium

In classical statistical mechanics, one has the example of equilibrium in a gas of N particles. This, however, is a physical situation for which one needs to identify the relevant properties of a particle associated in creating the equilibrium balance. Not every property is relevant. For example, a gas has particles which have momentum and energy, possibly related nonrelativistically by $e = pp/2m$, so e is relevant. These collide with each other, presumably elastically because one does not want to lose energy, and so the number of particles in a tiny volume should be related to the pressure. If there are pressure imbalances, there will not be a static equilibrium picture, so one considers a pressure balance as being the key to equilibrium in such a gas. Thus, we suggest that one must first determine the kind of physical balance which creates equilibrium and then identify the single particle properties which are associated with such a balance. In this case, a pressure balance depends on the number of particles in a small volume, the velocity of each and the momentum. Thus, there are three pieces of information. Given a constant mass m for each particle, this reduces to two pieces of information, the number of particles in a little volume and the momentum. We note that this is not the same as knowing the position of each particle. For pressure, it does not matter if one particle or another is at point r_1 as long as the momentum p is known. Thus, the particles are indistinguishable in space in this sense due to the requirements of pressure and not an ad hoc imposition of indistinguishable particles. The problem may be simplified if one knows the energy of each particle $pp/2m$ and how many particles exist in a small volume.

Minimizing Information

Once one knows the relevant information, one may try to minimize this information. For example, one needs to know how many particles are in a tiny volume. Given a large volume V , minimum information suggests that all tiny volumes have the same number of particles. Otherwise, one needs extra information which describes why one tiny volume has more particles than another. It is not necessary to know which particle is in which volume, only the total number of particles in each tiny volume. This is equivalent to treating the particles as indistinguishable in space. Furthermore, one only needs to know how many particles have a certain energy $e=pp/2m$ at each r point. It is known that physically, two body interactions occur and that these should be the same at each r point, on average, otherwise extra information is needed to distinguish between r points. If $P(e_1)$ is the probability to have energy e_1 , then a collision of e_1 and e_2 is associated with the probability $P(e_1)P(e_2)$, where $e_1+e_2=e$. If one had $e_3+e_4=e$ and assumed that $P(e_3)P(e_4)$ had a different value, there would need to be extra information to explain why e created from e_1 and e_2 had a different probability than e created from e_3 and e_4 . This leads to:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_i)P(e_j) \quad \text{where } P \text{ is unnormalized and } e_1+e_2 = e_i+e_j \quad ((1))$$

A solution is to have $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$ where C is a normalization constant and T a constant linked with average energy.

The Notion of Entropy

At this point, there is no notion of entropy. In the above sections, particle properties relevant to the physical equilibrium, a pressure balance in this case, were identified and then all unnecessary information related to these properties removed to find the solution:

A The number of particles in each tiny volume is the same.

B The energy distribution at each r point is $C \exp(-e/T)$.

One may link A and B to the number of states associated with the properties being considered. If one, however, wishes a property to pertain to a single particle, one has to use the following:

A One may consider the position r vector of a particle as long as one considers that the interchange of any particle with the same energy does not lead to a new state. This is the idea of indistinguishability and it follows from A because one only needs to know how many particles are in a tiny volume. In other words, if one has $n(e)$ particles with energy e , one may interchange these particles' positions without creating a new state because such a new state has nothing to do with pressure balance which is linked with A and B.

As a result, one may suggest that the number of states is proportional to:

$$[(\text{Sum over } e \exp(-e/T)) V / N!]^{\text{power } N} \quad ((2))$$

Here N is the number of particles in a volume V and $N!$ ensures that one does not count interchanges of the particles at positions in space as different. Given that ((2)) is a large number, one may take the logarithm \ln and call this quantity entropy.

If one defines the \ln of ((2)) as a quantity of interest, i.e. the \ln of the "states" of properties linked to pressure balance, with $1/N!$ being inserted because the r position of each state is not the property one needs to know, but rather A, then \ln of ((2)) is additive for the situation of a gas with two equal volume chambers with N particles of the same gas in each, as shown in Part I. It was also noted in Part I, that the same gas means that $e = pp/2m$ for each and m is the same, as these are the parameters needed to calculate pressure.

Maximization of Entropy

In the above section, the \ln of the number of states, related to the parameters of interest for pressure balance and compatible with this, i.e. indistinguishability, was called entropy. One may ask, however, What is the relevance of entropy? Why is it needed? We argued two sections above that by minimizing information associated with relevant particle parameters, one could find the spatial density and $P(e)$. Minimizing information should be a mathematical procedure associated with a function which is to be extremized subject to constraints. In the section above the previous, however, no mathematical minimization was performed. Rather, different arguments were used to find a constant spatial density and $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$.

We consider here whether entropy, defined above, may represent the quantity required. In such a case, we take spatial density as a given and try to find $P(e)$ still retaining the $1/N!$ indistinguishability feature associated with pressure balance. In such a case, if one has N particles

with $n(e) = NP(e)$ and N and $n(e)$ values are very large, then maximizing the expression $\ln (N! / \text{Product over } e \ n(e)!)$ subject to the constraint $\text{Sum over } e \ e \ n(e) = E_{ave}$ ((3)) yields: $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$ ((4)) using Stirling's approximation.

Thus, entropy has an important use as its extremization, subject to a constraint, leads to $P(e)$.

One must, however, construct this entropy, i.e. \ln of states, in a very special way by identifying states by parameters consistent with what is required for a balance (pressure balance in this case) which creates equilibrium. As a result, $1/N!$ appears in a natural manner, as pressure only depends on the number of particles in a tiny volume and not on which particles are present.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that an equilibrium is based on a physical balance. This balance, in turn, is linked with specific particle properties, although one must be a little careful. For example, for the case of $e = p^2/2m$, one may argue that pressure depends on p/m and p (proportional to impulse), but also to the number of particles at each r point. For simplicity, one may consider a one dimensional problem. The spatial density is not the same thing as knowing the exact position of a particle. If there are two particles with energy and the same momentum, then the pressure is identical if one is at r_1 and the other at r_2 or vice versa. Thus, one has one state and not two based on pressure and this is identical to indistinguishability which is usually cited in the literature, as argued in Part I. Once one knows which particle parameters are relevant, one may try to remove all unnecessary information associated with these parameters. Above, we argued that this leads to a constant spatial density and $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$. Minimizing information, however, should follow from the mathematical extremization of a function subject to a constraint(s). We suggest that this function is the \ln of the number of states based on the specially chosen parameters and consistent with the balance of pressure. For instance, if one has N particles and $n(e_i)$ particles with energy e_i , then $N!$ is the number of arrangements of the particles, but one must divide by $\text{Product over } e_i \ n(e_i)!$ because interchanging the positions of particles with the same e_i does not lead to a different state in terms of pressure. Thus, the notion of pressure is the driver of the factor $1/n(e_i)!$.